

marker #9A

0.02

marker #13A

0.02

marker #41

0.005

marker #44

0.004

marker #46

0.003

marker #50

0.004

marker #51_1

0.05

marker #52

0.005

marker #56

0.003

marker #57

0.006

marker #58

0.005

marker #63

0.004

100 116_01_Lgram_2
 100 273_02_Llith_1
 100 274_01_Llith_1
 100 162_03_Lhall_1
 208_01_Lhall_1
 100 090_01_Lburn_1
 99 092_02_Lburn_1
 99 280_05_Llaci_2
 99 055_03_Lplur_2
 100 062_02_Lcacu_1
 99 040_09_Lplur_2
 100 159_11_Lgall_1
 161_06_Lgall_2
 100 225_01_Lvirg_1
 250_01_Lvirg_2
 34 412_01_Lligu_1
 100 278_01_Ltrid_2
 4 278_05_Ltrid_2
 135_07_Lager_1
 99 184_01_Lvulg_1
 26 209_01_Lgaud_2
 90 266_02_Lpyre_2
 267_03_Lpyre_2
 86 L46_08_Lvulg_1
 276_01_Lgaud_1
 89 M60_01_Lager_1
 36 366_01_Llegr_2
 369_01_Llegr_1
 100 084_10_Lgrac_1
 085_04_Lgrac_2
 100 406_01_Lligu_2
 100 128_01_Lmons_1
 38 340_01_Lmons_1
 42 510_01_Lelia_1

70 280_03_Llaci_1
 280_05_Llaci_1
 57 412_01_Lligu_2
 96 366_01_Llegr_1
 87 040_09_Lplur_1
 45 135_07_Lager_2
 82 M60_01_Lager_2
 100 128_01_Lmons_2
 340_01_Lmons_2
 58 406_01_Lligu_1
 58 273_02_Llith_2
 274_01_Llith_2
 65 062_02_Lcacu_2
 100 159_11_Lgall_2
 161_06_Lgall_1
 4369 266_02_Lpyre_1
 225_01_Lvirg_2
 250_01_Lvirg_1
 15 446_01_Lrotu_1
 87 267_03_Lpyre_1
 87 068_01_Lcacu_1
 28 055_03_Lplur_1
 78 208_01_Lhall_2
 93 449_01_Lrotu_1
 92 162_03_Lhall_2
 12 L46_08_Lvulg_2
 209_01_Lgaud_1
 184_01_Lvulg_2
 7600 096_06_Lgram_1
 58 116_01_Lgram_1
 51 090_01_Lburn_2
 092_02_Lburn_2
 276_01_Lgaud_2
 89 278_01_Ltrid_1
 278_05_Ltrid_1
 57 100 084_10_Lgrac_2
 38 100 085_04_Lgrac_1
 100 504_01_Lelia_1
 510_01_Lelia_2

marker #62 (not included in species tree reconstruction)

0.06